

Sonification Mappings for Sensing Tree Stress: A DIY Approach

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ABSTRACT

Tree stress data is commonly obtainable through costly hardware devices, often requiring interpretation by scientists with existing background knowledge. However, such data can benefit laypeople’s tree management practices and raise climate change awareness. This work aims to discover suitable tree and climate data mappings to sound, for meaningful interpretation by non-specialists, using a low-cost, Do-it-Yourself (DIY) approach. A budget-friendly custom tree-talker prototype was created, streaming dendrometer, soil moisture, temperature, and humidity data to a web-based backend. A frontend web application explores differing complexities of sonified data mappings to users through the Web Audio API. We propose that distinct mappings will be required for clear data parameter interpretation, and inclusivity for users of diverse backgrounds. This initial exploration suggests that sonification presents a promising solution, with future work required to identify the most suitable environmental-to-sound mappings.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**; *Environmental sciences*; • **Human-centered computing** → Information visualization;

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Web Audio Conference WAC-2025, November 19–21, 2025, Paris, France.

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Figure 1: Workflow of hardware and software of our low-cost, DIY tree-talker prototype.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a world problem, with clear effects, revealed by natural disasters including summer droughts in Europe, and floods occurring worldwide, amongst other weather-related events. The general public often lacks clear local-level scientific information to assess the impact of climate change within their area, instead receiving global information in numerical or graphical forms. We seek to address this issue by adopting an artistic approach to inform audiences, trying to overcome the lack of access and likely limited understanding of the complex data scientists deal with.

Much of the scientific research on the impact of climate change on forests focuses on a limited number of intensively monitored areas [15, 17]. This lacks wide geographical vari-

ability, increasing the uncertainty when upscaling to a regional or national level for policy-making. We believe that offering artistic and simplified graphical/sonic interpretation of complex data and the ability to monitor nearby trees can help raise awareness of relevant issues caused by climate change to our forest ecosystem and contribute to a wider geographic data variability. Monitoring environmental conditions and tree stress over time benefits climate change awareness, bringing attention to the increased stress on trees caused by extreme weather events, and a changing climate.

We contribute to democratise science, through developing a low-cost Internet of Things (IoT) tree-talker prototype for the general public to use, in response to the expensive, bulky and complex commercial solutions, typically only used by scientists. Such device measures variables related to tree stress, including tree growth, air temperature, humidity, and soil moisture, piloted using community and citizen-science methodologies. Moreover, we propose the creation of an accompanying low-entry web application, for clear data analysis, visualisation, and sonification, that can be of interest to both the scientific and artistic communities. The main focus is answering: *What are suitable mappings (data-to-sound associations) from weather data to sound data that can raise awareness about climate change?*

We present the hardware design to elicit tree stress using environmental data. Then, we examine the custom backend and frontend software to facilitate the data transfer, which is required to develop a sonification and visualisation web application. Furthermore, we propose sonification mappings, from basic to complex, that we believe have the potential to present the captured data in a clear and identifiable manner, particularly for non-scientists. Figure 1 illustrates our vision.

2. BACKGROUND

As climate data becomes less visually predictable, researchers seek sonification as a method to convey complex, dynamic patterns in an accessible way [10, 14]. Traditional visual methods such as static charts or maps often fail to clearly show continuous changes over time in nature [9]. Researchers have turned to sonification—a method in which data is converted to sound—to solve this problem [7], as unlike traditional visual media, sound can transmit data continuously and in real time [11].

The value of sonification for climate data has been illustrated by recent experiments. Installations of Twedt [14], a researcher and sonic artist, converted forest microclimate data into hearable patterns, allowing participants to perceive forest cycles. Similarly, Kalonaris [8] transformed tropical CO₂ and solar radiation into sound textures, encouraging listener engagement with carbon cycles. St. George et al. [13] turned tree-ring records into musical notes, enabling audiences to hear long-term climate trends.

Lindborg et al. [9] showed that sonified weather data enhanced emotion and memory, especially when using direct mappings, like pitch for temperature. At the 2024 *Sensing the Forest* hackathon,¹ Ireti Olowe emphasised that sensor feedback should be physically understandable, using sound or touch to help users connect with environmental data, while discussing the customisation of mappings [12]. Our approach builds on the standard sonification techniques of

¹<https://bit.ly/4nAb8Tt>

Figure 2: Hardware configuration overview of the sensing unit.

Figure 3: A real-world deployment of the streaming unit.

parameter mapping sonification [5], which associates information with auditory parameters; and model-based sonification, which look into the processes to describe the evolution of a system over time [6]. Building on these insights, our current research explores low-cost, participatory devices to sonify real-time forest data. Integrating prior techniques [1, 3, 5, 6] and Olowe’s embodied interaction principles [12], this work aims to support broader public understanding and foster functional, revealing relationships with forest systems.

3. SYSTEM

3.1 Hardware

A custom tree-talker prototype is being iteratively developed to ensure affordability, modularity, and ease of use.² As illustrated in Figures 2 and 3, the system integrates a suite of sensors—including a capacitive soil moisture sensor, a combined temperature and humidity sensor, and a bespoke dendrometer—connected to a Raspberry Pi (RPi) Zero 2W for data acquisition and processing. Traditional dendrometer systems are often prohibitively expensive and require specialised expertise for installation, making them inaccessible for community-based ecological monitoring or low-budget research initiatives. To address this gap, we designed a low-cost dendrometer inspired by the open-source magnetic carbon-fibre dendrometer by Clonch et al. [2]. In our adaptation, we replaced the carbon-fibre frame with

²<https://github.com/sensingtheforest/Sensing-Unit-System-Code>

a durable, high-density PLA 3D-printed structure, significantly reducing the material cost and fabrication time while preserving mechanical stability.

The dendrometer’s main chassis is fastened securely around the tree or plant stem using a non-invasive, adjustable strap, allowing for stable attachment without inflicting damage or stress on the plant. A spring-loaded T-shaped magnet mount slides freely in response to micro-changes in the stem’s diameter—typically in the micrometer range—caused by natural growth or environmental conditions. These minute displacements are captured by the AS5311 linear magnetic position sensor, which tracks the relative motion of the magnet with high precision. The sensor sends a Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signal of the linear position to the RPi for real-time decoding and processing.

To support comprehensive environmental monitoring, the system also includes a capacitive soil moisture sensor and a temperature-humidity sensor, allowing the collected dendrometric data to be contextualised within prevailing microclimatic conditions. This enables the correlation of stem dynamics with soil moisture availability and ambient climatic fluctuations, facilitating more nuanced interpretations of plant physiological behaviour. As shown in Figure 2, the entire system is supported by a multi-source power setup, including a 45W USB-C RPi power supply, a 100W portable solar panel, and a 25000mAh power bank, ensuring autonomous field operation even in off-grid environments. For user interaction and data inspection, a 7” HDMI touch screen (1024×600 px resolution) is integrated into the system, with additional remote access capabilities via VNC Viewer to allow for headless operation and remote data monitoring.

3.2 Software

3.2.1 Backend

We created a customised web server using Express.js.³ The server allows sharing the data produced by the tree-talkers with the general public. The server is developed as a RESTful API, providing different functionalities through REST end points, corresponding to HTTP URLs. Each tree-talker posts a JSON file at regular times to a dedicated end point that the web server catches and stores in the server’s file system.⁴

3.2.2 Frontend

For each individual tree-talker unit, several REST end-points provide data management functionality, such as checking the latest JSON file sent by the unit, listing all generated JSON files, and verifying files as they are sent. This is useful to confirm that the unit works and that the values sent are correct. The JSON file data structure looks like this:

```
{ "timestamp": "2025-06-12 19:40:22",
  "temperature": 17.89,
  "humidity": 54.60,
  "soilmoisture": 60.03,
  "displacement in micrometer": 0.15 }
```

³<https://expressjs.com>

⁴<https://github.com/sensingtheforest/custom-web-server-backend>

Figure 4: Screenshot of the sensor data using Chart.js with temperature (red), humidity (blue), soil moisture (green) and displacement (yellow).

Each unit has a public end point which allows visualisation and sonification of the sensor data. Two bespoke web tools support this, described in the next section.

4. MAPPINGS

Next, we present two basic and two complex examples of sonification mappings within the frontend application.⁵

4.1 Basic

We propose two simple sonification mappings, whereby sensor data values can correspond to separate drone sounds or frequency modulation (FM) synthesiser parameters. Visualisations were developed using a progressive line chart from the Chart.js⁶ library (see Figure 4).

4.1.1 Drone Soundscape

A simple relationship between data and sound involves a direct, one-to-one mapping between data values and drone (low-frequency) sounds. The most basic and common drone mapping consists of creating one consistent starting auditory base tone (or musical note) for each received parameter, and varying the frequency (or musical pitch) of each tone with respect to the corresponding parameter value changes [4]. This can be achieved using a natural mapping, where higher sensor values correspond to higher tones or pitches [16]. As future work, these drone sounds may be played using different instruments or timbres, to aid distinguishability, particularly as the values change over time.

4.1.2 FM Synthesis Parameters

A further proposed basic mapping entails the control of parameters of a frequency modulation (FM) synthesiser from the data values, using a one-to-one mapping. FM synthesis parameters often include user controls for carrier frequency, modulator frequency, modulation index (depth of modulation), and carrier gain (output level) of the synthesiser voices. Similarly to the drone sounds, we propose a natural mapping, where the carrier frequency, modulator frequency, modulation index, and carrier gain can be calculated using suitably rescaled sensor values, with a higher reading corresponding to a higher carrier frequency, for instance [16]. One suggested mapping couples the temperature to the carrier frequency, humidity to the modulator

⁵Examples and code are available on the accompanying webpage: <https://sensingtheforest.github.io/wac2025/>

⁶<https://www.chartjs.org>

frequency, dendrometer reading to the modulation index, and soil moisture to the carrier gain.

4.2 Complex

We suggest two complex sonification mappings, where users can create their custom sonifications from the data, or sonifying parameters inferred from the sensor readings. Visualisations were developed using the D3.js⁷ library.

4.2.1 Custom Sonification

A custom sonification tool is proposed, whereby users themselves may design their own sonifications, benefitting user interaction, and allowing users to tailor the output audio to their own desires or ideas (Figure 5). As ongoing development, we suggest users may first select the instruments they wish to use to sonify each data variable, such as temperature being represented by a bass guitar, or humidity being sonified through a piano, custom instrument, or uploaded audio sample, later tailored to their personal preference. Users may adjust the tempo and rhythm for each value, or the piece as a whole, where tempo, rhythm and note duration can be mapped to the data variables, and select a scale or starting pitch for the tool to automatically map to notes, using the received sensor data. Unlike the basic sonifications, users may opt to use one-to-one, one-to-many or many-to-many mappings, depending on their selected options.

To increase the system’s musicality and value as a compositional tool, users may add chords or drums to the sonified output, either automatically based on pre-defined patterns or the input data, or manually. Moreover, each instrument track’s volume may be manually managed, alongside its panning and spatial location, and audio effects, including EQ, reverb, delay, distortion, and dynamic range compression, for performative and analytical benefit. Selecting suitable options from each section of the dropdown list-based tool will result in a final piece being generated based on the tree data over time, with full transport controls, individual instrument volumes, and saving functionality, to ensure users can best interpret the sonified data.

4.2.2 Inference

In addition to each sensor’s recorded value being mapped directly to an audible parameter, through utilising historical data readings, or performing calculations on multiple sensor values, further tree stress insights may be identified. Through mapping one day of dendrometer data to pitch, tree shrinkage and expansion may be identified through the increasing and decreasing notes played. After at least three months, sonification of the dendrometer and temperature readings, would present the tree’s response to the climate.

The tree’s mean growth may be inferred from its minimum and maximum dendrometer values, as a proxy of its water uptake: $\text{Tree Mean Growth} = \text{Maximum Expansion Point} - \text{Minimum Shrinkage Point}$. $\text{Mean Growth} = \text{Dendrometer}_{\text{max}} - \text{Dendrometer}_{\text{min}}$.

Humidity and temperature readings can be used to estimate the air dryness above the tree canopy, which drives water up the tree’s trunk. In a dry atmosphere, trees absorb more water to transpire into the atmosphere through the canopy. This can be combined with soil moisture and

Figure 5: Sonification instrument selection within the developed custom sonification web application.

humidity readings, with inference to identify if the tree is working hard (stressed), or if it can easily absorb the water it needs from the soil (unstressed). As seen, these inferred values may be sonified using a drone soundscape, FM synthesis parameter, or custom sonification mapping method.

5. DISCUSSION

Through mapping tree and environmental data using a one-to-one approach, particularly with each parameter mapped to pitch, used in the basic and inference sonifications, we suggest this could enable listeners to prominently hear changes in each sensor’s reading, and interplay of the different factors that influence a tree’s health, through initial experiments with the system. Although the hardware and software components have been designed and implemented, the proposed sonification approaches have not yet been tested with participants, and reflect the views of the authors, hence a user study is planned to confirm their suitability. The example sonifications, and impressions of the system itself, are promising for future work. Future refined custom sonifications may offer user retention, through benefiting interactivity and variability in the sonifications, while allowing a user to create the soundscape that best fits their artistic vision, or scientific area of interest.

6. CONCLUSION

This research presented the first steps towards basic and complex suitable mappings from weather data to sound data using a DIY tree-talker highlighting climate change phenomena. Future work is required to establish the suitability of the proposed mappings, particularly in relation to the most appropriate sonic outputs or synthesiser parameters for each type of data received from the sensors as well as validating its connection with raising awareness about climate change.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is part of the Sensing the Forest project, which has received funding from the UKRI Arts and Humanities Research Council (AH/X011585/2). Special thanks to Ireti Olowe for her valuable insights on mappings.

⁷<https://d3js.org>

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